

A socio-critical perspective in mathematics education: Doing interviews

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This paper aims to present a seminar proposal, to be developed during the summer semester of 2021 at Freie Universität Berlin, Germany, based on an on-going thesis. This seminar does reference to concepts like dreams, being more, background and foreground, from Critical Mathematics Education and Freire's Pedagogy, and aims to promote the study on the Interview research procedure from a socio-critical perspective in Mathematics Education. In this text, we briefly explore the thesis and seminar's theoretical framework, as well as present the implementation, highlighting the topics, the interview transcript, and some reflections that we can make about these works so far.

Introduction

This paper is about an ongoing seminar, given by the first author, based on interrelated concepts such as dreams, being more, background and foreground (Freire, 1983, 2000; Skovsmose, 2011, 2014).

For Paulo Freire (1983), human beings know themselves as unfinished, and therefore, they have hopes and dreams. They have hopes because of the human nature, that put themselves in a search movement, trying to be more. And human beings dream because they want to have experiences of humanization and freedom.

Inspired by this educator, we could say that dreams have a political perspective, related to the social, political, economic, and cultural contexts of human beings. They also have a subjective perspective, related to personal life experiences. It means that these dreams are historical and represent an important connection with human beings' backgrounds. Although these dreams make reference to the past, they are not defined by them because, as a part of the humanity's search movement, they point to the future, and generate foregrounds.

Foreground is a terminology named by Ole Skovsmose (2014), which refers to future perspectives, such as dreams, desires, hopes, obstacles, fears and frustrations. These foregrounds can be seen as landscapes of the future, those influenced by the past, but not determined by it.

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The seminar proposal was inspired by these concepts, as they are part of the first author's doctoral thesis (Soares, in progress). In her work, the research is being carried out based on Freire and Skovsmose's concepts, among others. The aim is to understand how teenagers from a social oppression context dream, what we can say about their life stories, and how they see the role of school and, specially, mathematics classes in helping them to develop their dreams. In the thesis, she works with teenagers from two schools: one in Sao Paulo, Brazil, and one in Bogota, Colombia. She refers to the case study and the life history (Goldemberg, 2004, Nogueira et al., 2017) as inspirations for and uses the interview as the most important data production procedure.

For the referred seminar, participants will be invited to produce data with students from public schools in Berlin, from diverse backgrounds. We will encourage them to be open to students from social oppression context, as was done in the thesis.

We understand that the inclusion of schools outside the Latin American context, in this case, from a German context, which is known as a more privileged region, will bring great gains for the scope of the research and for its impact. The inclusion of this new context will help to identify the dreams of young students from public schools in a global context, and expand the possibilities of mathematics classes in different classrooms around the world, about the understanding of these rooms as spaces that foster dreams and social transformation.

The seminar

The seminar has been prepared to be part of Freie Universität Berlin's course catalogue during the summer semester of 2021, as a result of the first author's work during her stay at this university, as part of a doctorate exchange period, and supervised by the second one. The seminar proposal was built pursuing the following general aim: to promote the study of an Interview research procedure, from a socio-critical perspective in Mathematics Education, based on the Case Study and Life History methodologies (Goldemberg, 2004, Nogueira et al., 2017). Another important approach for this seminar was the multicultural perspective in Mathematics Education (McLaren, 2000). The seminar will be arranged intending to develop a theoretical study in a dialogical way, and creating conditions for the participants to experience doing interviews in practice, going into the field to investigate the following guiding question: how Berlin teenagers dream, and what they think about school and Mathematics classes?

During the referred seminar, which will be held in English, participants (mainly bachelor's degree students) will be invited to produce data that will consist of semi-structured interviews, as in the thesis, with teenager students. At the end of the seminar, everyone will present their produced data and we, among the participants, will think about an initial interpretation of these data.

The interview script, that was also part of the first author's thesis, based on the theoretical framework and on the original one's (naturally, in Portuguese), is as follows:

Life:

1. Who are you?
2. How is your family?
3. How was your childhood?
4. And your adolescence so far, how was it?

Schools:

1. How were the schools that you have studied so far?
2. How do you relate to school, from childhood to today?
3. Who have been your math teachers since childhood?
Tell me a little about them and your relationship with them.
4. What do you think about mathematics classes?

Dreams:

1. Do you identify injustices with you, or in your environment, or in the world?
Which ones?
2. What makes you move on, or drives you?
3. What are your dreams? Why do you have these dreams?
4. How do you imagine yourself 4 years from now? And in 15 years?
5. If you were to choose a profession, what would it be?
(Say the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd place, and justify).
6. Would you change something in your life or in the world? What and why?

All these questions seek to respond the aim's thesis. Briefly, we can say that the first four questions were inspired by the life history methodology and the concept of background; the next four questions were also inspired by the life history methodology and include concerns about mathematics education, and the last six questions were inspired by the concepts of foreground and dreams, including concerns about social and political aspects.

The goals to be achieved with this seminar proposal were categorized into ten seminars which include the following topics: socio-Critical perspective in mathematics education; multicultural perspective in mathematics education; case study and life history - understanding the methodology; "how to make an interview?" - theoretical framework and presenting the semi-structured model; transcription and textualization of interviews - understanding the differences; and data production presentation and interpreting results based on the theoretical framework.

The classes will take place during the summer semester in 2021, between April and July. The topics, naturally, are related to the theoretical perspectives addressed in the thesis on which the seminar is based, except for the multicultural perspective. It was added due to the multiethnic and religious context in which many students in Berlin find themselves.

Last considerations

The thesis is at an advanced stage, and we could present in this text some of its results. For instance, we could say that families have a big impact on students' dreams, that their past experiences influence their foregrounds a lot, but not only 'negatively', and that many social oppressed students reveal, through their dreams, their desires for social justice. However, we think this is not the right place to share some of these initial conclusions because we tried here to focus on the seminar and, with this, we intend to look further, covering diverse backgrounds that go beyond.

Finally, in addition to the objectives linked to the thesis, we understand that the purpose of this referred seminar is that the participants learn in the field (in a practical way) how to conduct qualitative interviews in the socio-critical area, having a bibliographic basis in this regard, and start to learn how presenting research results and interpreting them.

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